

UNDERSTANDING THE LINK BETWEEN DARK PERSONALITY TRAITS AND MICROAGGRESSION IN EMERGING ADULTHOOD: EVIDENCE FROM PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The present study examined the relationship between Dark Tetrad personality traits and gendered and racial microaggressions among emerging adults in Pakistan. The Dark Tetrad consists of Machiavellianism, narcissism, psychopathy, and sadism, which have been associated with socially aversive behaviors and reduced empathy. Given the limited research on microaggressions within the Pakistani context, this study aimed to explore how dark personality traits relate to the perception and experience of microaggressions among emerging adults. A cross-sectional research design was employed, and data were collected from 291 participants aged 18 to 29 years through purposive sampling. Participants completed the Short Dark Tetrad (SD4) and the Gendered Racial Microaggressions Scale (GRMS). Pearson correlation analyses were conducted to examine relationships among demographic variables, dark personality traits, and microaggressions. The findings revealed significant positive associations between psychopathy, sadism, overall Dark Tetrad scores, and microaggression frequency and appraisal. Psychopathy demonstrated the strongest relationship with microaggressions. Age was negatively associated with both dark personality traits and microaggression experiences, indicating that younger participants reported higher levels of these variables. Gender differences were also observed, with males reporting higher levels of narcissism, psychopathy, and overall Dark Tetrad traits. The findings suggest that dark personality traits, particularly psychopathy and sadism, play an important role in shaping how individuals perceive, experience, and potentially engage in microaggressive behaviors. The study contributes to the growing literature on personality and discrimination by providing evidence from a non-Western cultural context and highlights the importance of considering personality characteristics when understanding subtle forms of discrimination.

INTRODUCTION

The term dark personality triad construct was first coined by Paulhus and Williams (2002) after the emerging interest in the dark side of personality but throughout the years more traits were added to the dark personality traits and it became from dark personality triad to tetrad, dyad, composite etc. (Kowalski et al., 2021). This research will focus on the dark personality tetrad which consists of Machiavellianism, narcissism, psychopathy, and sadism. The first trait, Machiavellianism, is defined by Jones and Paulhus (2013) as consisting of cynical worldview, lack of morality, and manipulateness. The same traits are used to define it by O'Boyle et al. (2012) and Paulhus and Williams (2002). Jones and Paulhus (2013) identified the defining characteristics of psychopathy, the second trait, to be impulsive and

low empathy. Paulhus and Williams' (2002) definition consists of these two characteristics with the addition of low anxiety, and O'Boyle et al (2012) further elaborate that a lack of guilt is another defining characteristic, and the combination of 4 these characteristics often leads to antisocial behavior. LeBreton et al. (2006) define the difference between clinical and subclinical psychopathy as a difference in severity rather than type of symptoms. They state that where clinical psychopathy impairs functioning to a chronically dysfunctional degree, subclinical psychopathy causes deficits in socioemotional functioning in terms of the defining characteristics, but not to a dysfunctional degree. The defining behaviors of the third trait, narcissism, as identified by Jones and Paulhus (2013) were manipulateness and callousness, like Machiavellianism and psychopathy. However, it is clarified that the motivation behind the behaviors is where narcissism differs, as they are motivated by reinforcement of a grandiose self-image, as opposed to the other two traits which are motivated by material or instrumental gain. O'Boyle et al. (2012) and Paulhus and Williams (2002) both emphasize dominance as another defining characteristic, with O'Boyle et al also mentioning the possibility of aggression as a feature in some cases. The last trait from the tetrad

is Sadism, Sadism involves deriving pleasure from the suffering of others. Traditionally, it has been examined in extreme contexts, such as criminal activities and sexual behavior, however, recent insights show that it is more widespread and that it has evolutionary origins. Severe sadistic behaviours, like the torture of civilians by military and law enforcement personnel, consistently documented across history and cultures, provide evidence that sadism extends beyond social conditioning (Paulhus & Dutton, 2016).

Conversely, societal restrictions on sadistic behaviors have gradually emerged in Western culture since the 14th century. For instance, while medieval France once accepted public acts of cruelty, such as the torture of animals for entertainment, such practices are now deemed unacceptable. Despite this shift, acknowledged the persistence of a less extreme form of sadism, referred to as "soft sadism" which continues to exist in modern societies and may be a common personality trait. In this context, the term everyday sadism describes socially permissible, subclinical sadistic tendencies that are still prevalent in contemporary culture. (Paulhus & Dutton, 2016). These four related but notably distinctive traits are the elements that the Dark Tetrad is constructed of. The distinctive differences previously discussed explain their individual nature, while the common characteristics that make it possible to classify them under one category, such as exploitation and manipulateness, are what make it possible to classify them under the single category of the Dark Tetrad. (Ardic&Ozsoy, 2016).

Microaggressions, subtle and often unintentional discriminatory behaviors, can be linked to the Dark Personality Tetrad (DPT). Machiavellianism, narcissism, psychopathy, and sadism—as individuals that are high in these traits have a higher likelihood to engage in such behaviors, whether intentionally or inadvertently.

Machiavellianism, defined by manipulation and strategic deceit, could lead individuals to use microaggressions to undermine others without harming their own social standing. This could include intentionally making subtle, offensive remarks to discreetly humiliate or insult others, especially in competitive environments. For

narcissistic individuals, who are driven by entitlement and self-importance, microaggressions could be in the form of dismissive attitudes, demeaning comments, or condescending behavior, without recognition of the harm they cause. They also reinforce social hierarchies with their insensitivity to the experiences of marginalized groups, since their self-centric narrative does not give importance to experiences, they are unaffected by.

The callousness, emotional detachment, and a lack of empathy which defines psychopathy also increases the likelihood of microaggressive behavior, as it leads to disregarding social norms and the emotional impact of words or actions. Unlike narcissists, who seek validation through their microaggressions, psychopaths may take part in them entirely out of indifference or as a way of exerting dominance. Lastly, sadism, which involves finding pleasure in others' suffering, plays an especially harmful role in microaggressions. This provides a way for individuals high in sadistic traits to find satisfaction in the discomfort, humiliation, or distress they cause through intentional microaggressions. Sadism involves a deliberate enjoyment of harm, which is unlike the other traits, making it especially dangerous in social and professional settings.

Together, these dark traits contribute to the perpetuation of microaggressions, whether through manipulation, entitlement, indifference, or outright enjoyment of others' suffering, ultimately leading to adverse psychological effects on marginalized individuals. (Furnham & Treglown, 2024). Research shows that DPT plays a significant role in Micro-aggression. As the individuals with DPT are very manipulative and lack empathy they indulge in micro-aggression more than individuals without DPT. People with DPT are very cold, calculated and unempathetic towards other people and they do indulge in micro-aggression against already marginalized communities because they may see them as competition and would likely be micro-aggressive towards them (Moor et al., 2019).

The rationale behind this study is to identify gaps in the existing research and try to incorporate the psychological aspects with which the dark

personality traits effect microaggression and how microaggression is perceived in emerging adults. Taking a closer look at the demographic variables such as age, gender, profession, Income, and education level and to look how people with different backgrounds and experiences view microaggression and people who score high in dark personality tetrad, how the demographics play a part in developing these traits. As there is very little research on microaggression in Pakistan this study will bridge the gap on how people in Pakistan get microaggressive and how they experience microaggression done against them. The existing research is based on the western culture, but this study will give a context to the eastern culture (Pakistan).

Objectives:

- To examine the relationship between Dark Tetrad personality traits (Machiavellianism, Narcissism, Psychopathy, and Sadism) and microaggressions among emerging adults in Pakistan.
- To determine the extent to which each Dark Tetrad trait predicts experiences and perceptions of microaggressions.
- To investigate the association between the individual dimensions of microaggressions and Dark Tetrad personality traits.
- To examine gender differences in Dark Tetrad personality traits and microaggressions among emerging adults.
- To assess the contribution of demographic variables (e.g., age, gender, education level, employment status, and income) in explaining variations in dark personality traits and microaggressions.

Methodology

The current paper was extracted from a larger research project and a cross-sectional design was used to explore the study objectives.

Participants

There were 292 adults between 18 and 29 years of age that made up the sample, that were selected through nonprobability purposive sampling technique from different universities in Lahore.

The sample included both women and men. The sample size was determined through g-power analysis.

Measures

The following measures were used to collect the research data.

Demographic questionnaire

A detailed demographic questionnaire was utilized to record the participants’ personal information including their medical and psychiatric history. Short dark Tetrad (SD4) developed by Paulhus (2020) to assess dark personality traits SD4 was used. It is a five-point Likert scale questionnaire where 1 stands for strongly disagree and 5 stands for strongly agree. The SD4 is a brief (28-item) self-report measure designed to assess several dimensions of personality, naming machiavellianism, narcissism, psychopathy, and sadism. For the SD4, Cronbach’s alpha values typically range from 0.70 to 0.85 for the different subscales, indicating good internal consistency. The study by Jones and Paulhus (2014) reported the following Cronbach’s alpha values for the Dark Triad (precursor to the SD4): Machiavellianism ($\alpha = 0.76$), narcissism ($\alpha = 0.84$), and psychopathy ($\alpha = 0.78$). Test-retest reliability measures the stability of the instrument over time. Studies have shown that the SD4 has adequate test-retest reliability, with coefficients typically above 0.70 over periods of several weeks. (Paulhus et al., 2021). The **Gendered Racial Microaggressions Scale (GRMS)** was used to assess gendered microaggressions. It is a 26-item tool that is used to measure every day and subtle gendered racism experienced by women. The frequency of these experiences over the last year were reported by study participants on a 5-point Likert-type scale

with the following response options, 0: “never”, 1: “less than once a year”, 2: “a few times a year”, 3: “about once a month”, and 4: “a few times a month or more”. A total mean frequency score was calculated by averaging scores. Convergent validity is indicated by significant positive correlations with measures of perceived sexist events and microaggressions. GRMS frequencies have had good internal consistency reliability estimates with community-based samples of women. Originally the GRMS was developed to assess gendered racial microaggressions on a societal level. (Lewis and Neville 2015).

Procedure

Firstly, the research was presented to and approved by the relevant ethical and research review bodies, followed by formal approval obtained from the appropriate authorities as well as individual participants for data collection. The data was collected by the researcher in person using a survey booklet specifically compiled for this research. Each participant received identical copies of the booklet, which presented the data collection instruments in the same order. Although the measures were self-report, the researcher stayed present to aid or clarification if needed. After data collection, the researcher thanked each participant for their participation. Careful attention was given to adhering to all relevant ethical guidelines, provided by the Ethical Review Committee (ERC) and the Institutional Review Board (IRB). The proper permissions were obtained from the authors to use the scales, and participants were provided with required details about the study. They were briefed about their rights, including their ability to participate voluntarily and withdraw at any time. Their privacy was strictly respected, ensuring that no violations occurred.

Results

Table 1

Demographic Information of Sample (n=291)

Demographic Variables	f	%	M	SD
Gender				
Male	121	41.6		
Female	170	58.4		

Profession		
Employed	75	25.8
Unemployed	216	74.2
Education Level		
Intermediate	28	9.6
Bachelors	219	75.3
Postgraduate	44	15.1
Monthly income		158556 224205

Note. N = 291 for all variables except Monthly Income, for which N = 106.

Table 1 presents the demographic variables of the study participants (N = 291). The sample consisted of 170 females (58.4%) and 121 males (41.6%). A majority of participants were unemployed (74.2%), while 25.8% were employed. Regarding educational attainment, most participants were enrolled in or had completed a bachelor's degree

(75.3%), followed by postgraduate education (15.1%) and intermediate education (9.6%). For participants who reported their monthly income (n = 106), the average monthly income was PKR 158,556 (SD = 224,205), indicating substantial variability in income levels across respondents.

Table 2
Correlation Coefficients of demographic variables and SD4

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Age	—									
2. Profession	-.16**	—								
3. Gender	.10	-.11	—							
4. Education	.46**	-.24**	-.04	—						
5. Monthly Income	.03	.24*	.04	.11	—					
6. Crafty (Machiavellianism)	-.04	.02	.06	-.02	-.15	—				
7. Special (Narcissism)	-.03	-.06	.12*	.03	-.08	.30**	—			
8. Wild (Psychopathy)	-.20**	-.00	.22**	-.08	-.02	.23**	.42**	—		
9. Mean (Sadism)	-.13*	-.02	.19**	-.07	-.12	.23**	.27**	.55**	—	
10. SD4Total	-.15*	-.02	.22**	-.05	-.13	.57**	.69**	.80**	.77**	—

Note. SD = Short Dark Tetrad, Pearson correlation coefficients are reported. p < .05. ** p < .01

Table 2 presents the correlations between demographic variables and the dimensions of the Short Dark Tetrad (SD4). Age showed significant negative correlations with the Wild (Psychopathy) dimension (r = -.20, p < .01), Mean (Sadism) dimension (r = -.13, p < .05), and SD4 Total scores (r = -.15, p < .05), suggesting that younger participants reported higher levels of psychopathic, sadistic, and overall dark personality traits. Gender was positively associated with the Special (Narcissism) dimension (r = .12, p < .05),

Wild (Psychopathy) dimension (r = .22, p < .01), Mean (Sadism) dimension (r = .19, p < .01), and SD4 Total scores (r = .22, p < .01), indicating gender-related differences in dark personality characteristics. No significant associations were found between profession, education, monthly income, and the SD4 dimensions. The SD4 subscales were positively intercorrelated, with the strongest association observed between Wild and Mean (r = .55, p < .01), supporting the related yet distinct nature of the dark personality traits.

Table 3
Correlation Coefficients of demographic variables and GRM factors

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Age	—							
2. Profession	-.16**	—						
3. Education	.46**	-.24**	—					
4. Monthly Income	.03	.24*	.11	—				
5. Gender	.10	-.11	-.04	.04	—			
6. GRMF	-.12*	-.01	-.03	-.02	.10	—		
7. GRM Appraisals	-.10	.02	-.02	-.01	-.01	.80**	—	
8. GRMT	-.12*	.01	-.03	-.02	.05	.95**	.95**	—

Note. . GRMF = Gender and Racial Microaggression Frequency, GMRA = Gender and Racial Microaggression Appraisal, GRMTTotal = Gender and Racial Microaggression Total, $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$

Table 3 presents the relationships between demographic variables and Gender and Racial Microaggression (GRM) factors. Age demonstrated significant negative correlations with GRMF ($r = -.12, p < .05$) and GRMT ($r = -.12, p < .05$), indicating that younger participants reported greater frequencies and overall levels of microaggression experiences. No significant relationships were observed between profession,

education, monthly income, gender, and the GRM variables. Strong positive correlations were observed among the GRM dimensions themselves, with GRMF strongly correlated with GRM Appraisals ($r = .80, p < .01$) and GRMT ($r = .95, p < .01$). Similarly, GRM Appraisals showed a very strong positive relationship with GRMT ($r = .95, p < .01$), demonstrating excellent internal consistency among the GRM construct

Table 4
Correlation Matrix for Study Variables

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1. Age	—												
2. Profession	.16*	—											
3. Education	.46*	-.24**	—										
4. Monthly Income ¹	.03	.24*	.11	—									
5. Gender	.10	-.11	-.04	.04	—								
6. GRMF	-.12*	-.01	-.03	-.02	.10	—							
7. GRM Appraisals	-.10	.02	-.02	-.01	-.01	.80**	—						
8. GRMT	-.12*	.01	-.03	-.02	.05	.95**	.95**	—					
9. Crafty (Machiavellianism)	-.04	.02	-.02	-.15	.06	.13*	.10	.12*	—				

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
10. Special (Narcissism)	-.03	-.06	.03	-.08	.12*	.07	-.02	.03	.30**	—			
11. Wild (Psychopathy)	.20*	-.00	-.08	-.02	.22**	.40**	.26**	.35**	.23**	.42**	—		
12. Mean (Sadism)	-.13*	-.02	-.07	-.12	.19**	.34**	.22**	.29**	.23**	.27**	.55*	—	
13. SD4Total	-.15*	-.02	-.05	-.13	.22**	.35**	.21**	.29**	.57**	.69**	.80*	.77*	—

Note. SD = Short Dark Tetrad, GRMF = Gender and Racial Microaggression Frequency, GMRA = Gender and Racial Microaggression Appraisal, GRMTotal = Gender and Racial Microaggression Total, Monthly Income has a smaller sample size (n = 106). p < .01**, p < .05*

Table 4 presents the correlation matrix for all demographic and study variables. Age was negatively associated with GRMF (r = -.12, p < .05), GRMT (r = -.12, p < .05), Wild (Psychopathy) (r = -.20, p < .01), Mean (Sadism) (r = -.13, p < .05), and SD4 Total scores (r = -.15, p < .05), suggesting that younger individuals reported higher levels of both dark personality traits and microaggression experiences. Gender demonstrated positive correlations with Special (Narcissism) (r = .12, p < .05), Wild (Psychopathy)

(r = .22, p < .01), Mean (Sadism) (r = .19, p < .01), and SD4 Total scores (r = .22, p < .01). Significant positive relationships were also observed between microaggression variables and dark personality traits, particularly Wild (Psychopathy), Mean (Sadism), and SD4 Total scores. The strongest associations emerged between GRMF and Wild (r = .40, p < .01), indicating that individuals with higher psychopathic tendencies reported greater frequencies of microaggressive experiences.

Table 5
Correlations between SD4 and GRM

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Crafty (Machiavellianism)	—							
2. Special (Narcissism)	.30**	—						
3. Wild (Psychopathy)	.23**	.42**	—					
4. Mean (Sadism)	.23**	.27**	.55**	—				
5. SD4Total	.57**	.69**	.80**	.77**	—			
6. GRMF	.13*	.07	.40**	.34**	.35**	—		
7. GRM Appraisals	.10	-.02	.26**	.22**	.21**	.80**	—	
8. GRMT	.12*	.03	.35**	.29**	.29**	.95**	.95**	—

Note. SD = Short Dark Tetrad, GRMF = Gender and Racial Microaggression Frequency, GMRA = Gender and Racial Microaggression Appraisal, GRMTotal = Gender and Racial Microaggression Total, p < .01**, p < .05*

Table 5 presents the relationships between Dark Tetrad personality traits and Gender and Racial Microaggressions. Significant positive associations were found between several dark personality

dimensions and microaggression variables. The Wild (Psychopathy) dimension demonstrated the strongest relationships with GRMF (r = .40, p < .01), GRM Appraisals (r = .26, p < .01), and

GRMT ($r = .35, p < .01$), indicating that individuals with higher psychopathic traits reported greater frequency and intensity of microaggression experiences. Similarly, the Mean (Sadism) dimension was positively correlated with GRMF ($r = .34, p < .01$), GRM Appraisals ($r = .22, p < .01$), and GRMT ($r = .29, p < .01$). SD4 Total scores also showed significant positive relationships with GRMF ($r = .35, p < .01$), GRM Appraisals ($r = .21, p < .01$), and GRMT ($r = .29, p < .01$). In contrast, Crafty (Machiavellianism) showed only weak positive associations with GRMF ($r = .13, p < .05$) and GRMT ($r = .12, p < .05$), while Special (Narcissism) demonstrated no significant relationships with the GRM variables. Overall, these findings suggest that psychopathic and sadistic personality features are most strongly associated with greater experiences and perceptions of gender and racial microaggressions among emerging adults.

Discussion

The present study explored the relationships among demographic variables, Short Dark Tetrad (SD4) traits, including crafty (Machiavellianism), special (Narcissism), wild (Psychopathy), mean (Sadism) and the total score of the SD4 scale and gender and racial microaggression (GRM) factors, including Gender and Racial Microaggression Frequency (GRMF), Gender and Racial Microaggression Appraisal (GRMA), and Gender and Racial Microaggression Total (GRMT). The findings provide meaningful insights into how demographic characteristics and dark personality traits relate to the perception and experience of microaggressions.

The descriptive statistics showed that the demographic variables of the sample comprised of more women (58%), more participants were unemployed and had high education levels mostly completing 16 years of education. There was a positive relationship between age and education level and a negative relationship was noted between education and profession this was mainly due to many participants being students.

Profession and monthly income had a positive relationship, this is mainly due to financial stability is directly proportional to being

employed. Many participants were hesitant to disclose their monthly family income and that hinders with the result.

When the relationship between the demographic variables and the study variables was viewed, it showed that age had a significant negative relationship with wild (Psychopathy), mean (Sadism) and the total SD4 scores. The results are consistent with present research as people belonging to a younger age group, as development takes place and individuals develop socializing skills and they mature these traits decrease. (Jonason et al., 2017).

A difference between genders was also noted regarding the SD4 total scores and specifically Special (Narcissism) and wild (psychopathy). Males scored higher on the Dark tetrad traits more specifically Special (Narcissism) and wild (psychopathy). This aligns with the existing literature where males are more prone to get involved in socially aversive traits to gain control, be dominant and are likely to be more thrill seeking and have low empathy. (Jonason & Webster, 2010). Moreover, a strong correlation was found between the SD4 total scores and Wild (Psychopathy) further adding to the existing research that individuals having high disposition towards the dark personality tetrad tend to be involved in socially aversive behaviors. (Moshagen et al., 2018).

The other study variable, microaggression was measured by gendered and racial microaggression scale. Gendered and racial microaggression frequency (GRMF) and gendered and racial microaggression total (GRMT) had negative correlation with age. Showing that people who were younger reported higher frequency of microaggression faced and reported higher perception of microaggression experienced. This is due to the increase in awareness and generational differences. As people are more sensitive towards such behaviors they perceive and experience it in higher frequency and intensity. Younger individuals are more prone to notice such biases as they are more aware and more connected hence, they can identify and challenge such instances. Sue et al. (2007). The gendered and racial microaggression scale also showed strong

intercorrelation with all its subscales (GRMF, GRMA and GRMT). This indicates strong internal consistency and supports the interpretations and findings of this scale accurately measuring the microaggression experiences. These findings validate the structural integrity of the GRM construct within this sample.

The focus of this study was to determine the relationship between the dark personality traits (sd4) and the gendered and racial microaggression (GRM). The subscale of SD4, Wild (psychopathy) showed the strongest correlation with all the GRM subscales. The total SD4 score, and the subscale mean (Sadism) showed a positive correlation with all the GRM subscales. These findings show that individuals who have strong disposition towards the dark personality traits experience a greater frequency and intensity of microaggression, the individuals who score high on the SD4 total score or any of its subscales are more likely to indulge in microaggressive behaviors outwardly. This can be attributed to low empathy, high impulsivity, antagonism and reduced pro-social behavior. They might be callous towards other feelings and engage in microaggressive behaviors. Another interpretation of the results can be, that individuals with high SD4 scores are more vigilant towards the actions or behaviors directed towards them and with their personalities being selfish and psychopathic they may perceive things as hostile or derogatory. Wilkowski and Robinson (2010)

The findings of this study further the existing literature, personality shapes behaviors but also influences the interpretation of behaviors and social experiences. Microaggression are seen as external behaviors, but this study shows that personal differences specifically dark personality traits influence how microaggressive behaviors are perceived, appraised, and reported.

Conclusion:

The result of this study shows that how individuals interpret and react to social situations and behavior is influenced by personality and specially the personality traits within the dark personality tetrad. Individuals with high dark traits might have the tendency to be more prone to be microaggressive towards others and at the same

time may perceive interpersonal interactions as discriminatory or attacking towards themselves.

The study also adds to the existing literature, that the personality traits shape how individuals behave and perceive behaviors specifically experiences of gender and racial microaggression. Understanding The connection between the dark personality tetrad and gender and racial microaggression can be helpful in planning interventions and help us to better understand the experience, interpretation, appraisal, and reporting of subtle form of discriminations.

Limitations

The current study has several limitations that need to be acknowledged. The sample was collected using purposive sampling, which further reduces the generalizability of the results. Moreover, purposive sampling is prone to sampling bias. Since participants are chosen based on specific criteria, there is a higher likelihood of excluding diverse perspectives and experiences, leading to a biased sample. The constructs of dark personality traits, negative problem orientation, and microaggressions are complex and multifaceted. The measures used in the study may not capture all relevant dimensions or nuances, potentially leading to an incomplete understanding of these variables. The study may not account for environmental factors that influence the relationship between dark personality traits and microaggressions, such as peer influence, family dynamics, or socio-economic status. These factors can play a significant role in shaping behavior and should be considered in future research.

The study addresses sensitive topics, such as dark personality traits and microaggressions, which may evoke strong emotional reactions from participants. Ensuring ethical protocols and support systems for participants is crucial to address any distress that may arise during the research process.

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